

AN EOQ MODEL FOR DECAYING ITEMS UNDER THE CONDITION OF PERMISSIBLE DELAY IN PAYMENT

S. R. Singh, P. K. Saini & Rekha Chaudhary

Abstract: The purpose of this paper is to investigate the retailer's optimal replenishment policy under permissible delay in payments. All previously published articles dealing with optimal order quantity with permissible delay in payments assumed that the supplier only offers the retailer fully permissible delay in payments if the retailer ordered a sufficient quantity. Otherwise, permissible delay in payments would not be permitted. However, in this paper, we want to extend this extreme case by assuming that the supplier would offer the retailer fully permissible delay in payments when the order quantity is also smaller than a predetermined quantity and supplier would check the order quantity only at a specified time period which is greater than to the credit period.

Keyword: EOQ model, Trade credit, Deterioration.

1. INTRODUCTION

Every venture thrives on a customer policy which best suits its needs. Some people offer discounts as part of their policy, while some offer free gifts with their products. The policies may be different, but the basic requirement is the same-to fix the customer. The trend in this field has also seen a radical change with time as time has affected the business senses of organizations to a great extent. To keep apace with the changing trends, vendors sometimes offer concessions or credit limits to their customers. This means that the customer can take the goods home without having to pay for them immediately. They are allowed a certain time period to settle the accounts. Till the end of this time period, the customer is free to clear the financial credit at any time and is not required to pay any interest or penalty. Goyal [8] derived an EOQ model under the conditions of permissible delay in payments. Aggarwal and Jaggi [2] then extended Goyal's model to allow for deteriorating items. Next, Jamal *et al.*, [9] further generalized the model to allow for shortages. Liao *et al.*, [10] developed an inventory model for stock-depend consumption rate when a delay in payment is permissible. Recently, Arcelus *et al.*, [1] analyzed the pros and cons of price discount vs. trade credit. There were several interesting and relevant papers related to trade credits such as Shah [11,12], Chu *et al.*, [5], Chung [6], Chang *et al.*, [4], Chang and Dye [3], and Teng [13].

During the past few years, many researchers have studied inventory models for deteriorating items such as volatile liquids, blood banks, medicines, electronic components

and fashion goods. Deterioration of physical goods is one of the important factors in any inventory and production system. If the rate of deterioration is very low its effect can be ignored. But in many practical situations deterioration plays an important role. It is important to control and maintain the inventories of decaying items for the modern corporation. Ghare and Schrader [7] were the first proponents for developing a model for an exponentially decaying inventory. Teng *et al.*, [14] and Yang *et al.*, [15] further generalized the demand function to include any non-negative, continuous function that fluctuates with time.

In all the previously published articles dealing with optimal order quantity with permissible delay in payments assumed that, the supplier only offers the retailer fully permissible delay in payments if the retailer place an order of sufficient quantity otherwise, permissible delay in payments would not be permitted. However, in this paper, we want to extend this extreme case by assuming that the supplier would offer to the retailer fully permissible delay in payments whenever the order quantity is also lesser than predetermined quantity or sufficient quantity on the behalf of extra interest paid by retailer. On the other hand retailer gets all benefits of trade credit because supplier would check the order quantity only at a specified time period which is greater than to the credit period. This is the period at which retailer will pay extra interest rate because supplier would adopt DOQ (Displaying Order Quantity) policy which will work like as, if retailer's order quantity just below to a predetermined quantity W which is decided by supplier, then supplier will charge extra interest or fine upon retailer only at the specified period by the rate that lesser to the interest rate. Furthermore, supplier would offer to the retailer fully permissible delay in payment at the credit period and interest charge would remain unchanged up to the period at which DOQ policy would be start.

2. MODEL FORMULATION

2.1 Notations

D	demand rate per unit time.
A	ordering cost per unit time (order).
c	units purchasing price per item.
s	unit selling price.
$(h + Ht)$	unit stock holding cost per item per unit time excluding interest charges and where ' H ' is a positive constant and $(H < h)$.
I_e	interest earned per \$ per unit time.
I_k	interest charged per \$ in stocks per unit time by the supplier.

I_p	interest charged per \$ during the period ($T \geq M$) in stocks per unit time by supplier.
θ	fraction of units that deteriorate per time unit.
M	the supplier's period for adopting the DOQ policy per unit time.
N	the retailer's trade credit period offered by supplier per unit time.
Q	the order quantity.
T	the cycle time.
$TVC(T)$	the annual total variable cost which is a function of T.
W	the minimum order quantity at which interest charged is permitted.
T^*	the optimal replenishment cycle time which minimizes $TVC(T)$ when $T > 0$.
$Q^* = DT^*$	

2.2 Assumptions

1. Demand rate is known and constant.
2. Shortages are not allowed.
3. Replenishment rate is instantaneous.
4. There is no repair or replenishment of the deteriorated inventory during a given cycle.
5. The constant fraction θ of on hand inventory gets deterioration per time unit.
6. $I_k \geq I_e$, $M > N$.
7. When $T \geq N$, the account is settled at $T = N$ and the retailer starts paying for the interest charges on the items in stocks with rate I_k . When $T \leq N$ the account is settled at $T = N$ and the retailer does not need to pay.
8. The retailer can accumulate revenue and earn interest after its customer pays for the amount of purchasing cost to the retailer until the end of the trade credit period offered by the supplier.
9. $I_k \geq I_e \geq I_p$, $M > N$.

Interest charge is taken by supplier during the period (M) as,

$$\begin{cases} I_k, & T \geq W/D \\ (I_k + I_p), & T < W/D \end{cases}$$

That is, when the quantity in order of retailer to supplier is less than the fixed quantity then, the supplier will take interest charge at the rate $(I_k + I_p)$ to the retailer i.e. I_p is extra charge or fine, otherwise payments for the ordered quantity will be made with usual interest rate I_k .

2.3 The model

Let $Q(t)$ denote the on hand inventory level at time t , which is depleted by the effect of demand and deterioration, then the differential equation which describes the instantaneous states of $Q(t)$ over $(0, T)$ is given as:

$$\frac{dQ(t)}{dt} + \theta Q(t) = -D \quad 0 \leq t \leq T.$$

Then, with boundary condition $Q(T) = 0$, we get the solution of the above equation:

$$Q(t) = \frac{D}{\theta} \{e^{\theta(T-t)} - 1\} \quad 0 \leq t \leq T.$$

Noting that $Q(0) = Q$, the quantity order each replenishment cycle is:

$$Q = \frac{D}{\theta} (e^{\theta T} - 1).$$

Then, using the DOQ policy, we analysis of the optimal inventory policy in the presence of the trade credit. The annual total relevant cost consists of the following elements; there are two situations to arise: First $(N < M \leq W/D)$ & Second $(N < W/D < M)$

2.4 Suppose that $(N < M \leq W/D)$

(a) Average ordering cost = $\frac{A}{T}$

(b) Average inventory holding cost (excluding the capital opportunity cost)

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{(h + Ht)}{T} \int_0^T Q(t) dt \\ &= \frac{D(H + h\theta)}{T\theta^3} (e^{\theta T} - 1 - \theta T) - \frac{DHT}{2\theta} \end{aligned}$$

(c) Average cost of deteriorated units

$$= \frac{c}{\theta} \frac{D}{T} (e^{\theta T} - 1 - \theta T)$$

(d) From assumptions (7), (8) and (9) there are four sub-cases in terms of annual opportunity cost of the capital.

(i) If $(W/D \leq T)$, then average opportunity cost of capital

$$= \frac{cDI_k}{T\theta^2} [e^{\theta(T-N)} - \theta(T-N) - 1] - \frac{sDI_e N^2}{2T}$$

(ii) If $(M \leq T \leq W/D)$, then average opportunity cost of capital

$$= \frac{cDI_k}{T\theta^2} [e^{\theta(T-N)} - \theta(T-N) - 1] + \frac{cDI_p}{T\theta^2} [e^{\theta(T-M)} - \theta(T-M) - 1] - \frac{sDI_e N^2}{2T}$$

(iii) If $(N \leq T < M)$, then average opportunity cost of capital

$$= \frac{cDI_k}{T\theta^2} [e^{\theta(T-N)} - \theta(T-N) - 1] - \frac{sDI_e N^2}{2T}$$

(iv) If $(0 < T < N)$, then average opportunity cost of capital

$$= \left[\frac{sDI_e T}{2} + sI_e D(N - T) \right]$$

From the above conditions, the annual total relevant cost for the retailer can be expressed as $TVC(T) =$ ordering cost + stocks holding cost + opportunity cost + cost of deteriorated units.

Figure 1: The Inventory Level and the Total Saved Amount of Interest Payable when $(N < M \leq \frac{W}{D})$

$$TVC(T) = \begin{cases} TVC_1(T) & \text{if } W/D \leq T & \dots(a) \\ TVC_2(T) & \text{if } M \leq T \leq W/D & \dots(b) \\ TVC_3(T) & \text{if } N \leq T < M & \dots(c) \\ TVC_4(T) & \text{if } 0 < T < N & \dots(d) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where

$$TVC_1(T) = \frac{A}{T} + \frac{D\{\theta(c\theta + h) + H\}}{T\theta^3} (e^{\theta T} - 1 - \theta T) - \frac{DHT}{2\theta} + \frac{cDI_k}{T\theta^2} [e^{\theta(T-N)} - \theta(T-N) - 1] - \frac{sDI_e N^2}{2T}. \quad (2)$$

$$TVC_2(T) = \frac{A}{T} + \frac{D\{\theta(c\theta + h) + H\}}{T\theta^3} (e^{\theta T} - 1 - \theta T) - \frac{DHT}{2\theta} + \frac{cDI_k}{T\theta^2} [e^{\theta(T-N)} - \theta(T-N) - 1] + \frac{cDI_p}{T\theta^2} [e^{\theta(T-M)} - \theta(T-M) - 1] - \frac{sDI_e N^2}{2T}. \quad (3)$$

$$TVC_3(T) = \frac{A}{T} + \frac{D\{\theta(c\theta + h) + H\}}{T\theta^3} (e^{\theta T} - 1 - \theta T) - \frac{DHT}{2\theta} + \frac{cDI_k}{T\theta^2} [e^{\theta(T-N)} - \theta(T-N) - 1] - \frac{sDI_e N^2}{2T}. \quad (4)$$

$$TVC_4(T) = \frac{A}{T} + \frac{D\{\theta(c\theta + h) + H\}}{T\theta^3} (e^{\theta T} - 1 - \theta T) - \frac{DHT}{2\theta} - \left[\frac{sDI_e T}{2} + sI_e D(T-N) \right]. \quad (5)$$

Since $TVC_1(W/D) \leq TVC_2(W/D)$, $TVC_2(M) = TVC_3(M)$, $TVC_3(N) = TVC_4(N)$ $TVC(T)$ is continuous except at $T = W/D$ and well defined on $T > 0$. All $TVC_1(T)$, $TVC_2(T)$, $TVC_3(T)$, $TVC_4(T)$, $TVC(T)$ are defined on $T > 0$.

2.5 Suppose that $(N < W/D < M)$

The average total variable cost function can be expressed as $TVC(T)$ = ordering cost + stocks holding cost + opportunity cost + cost of deteriorated units.

$$TVC(T) = \begin{cases} TVC_1(T) & \text{if } M \leq T & \dots(a) \\ TVC_5(T) & \text{if } W/D \leq T \leq M & \dots(b) \\ TVC_3(T) & \text{if } N \leq T < W/D & \dots(c) \\ TVC_4(T) & \text{if } 0 < T < N & \dots(d) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Where

$$TVC_5(T) = \frac{A}{T} + \frac{D\{\theta(c\theta + h) + H\}}{T\theta^3} (e^{\theta T} - 1 - \theta T) - \frac{DHT}{2\theta} + \frac{cDI_k}{T\theta^2} [e^{\theta(T-N)} - \theta(T-N) - 1] - \frac{sDI_e N^2}{2T}. \quad (7)$$

Since $TVC_1(M) = TVC_5(M)$, $TVC_5(W/D) = TVC_3(W/D)$ and $TVC_3(N) = TVC_4(N)$, $TVC(T)$ is continuous and well defined on $T > 0$. All $TVC_1(T)$, $TVC_5(T)$, $TVC_3(T)$, $TVC_4(T)$ and $TVC(T)$ are defined on $T > 0$.

3. THE CONVEXITY

Here, we shall do that, five inventory functions described as above section are convex on their appropriate domains. Before proofing the convexity we shall proof some lemmas in this concern.

Lemma 1: $e^{\theta(T-N)} - 1 - \theta T e^{\theta(T-N)} + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2} e^{\theta(T-N)} + \theta N - \frac{N^2 \theta^2}{2} > 0$, if $(T \geq N)$.

Proof: let $g(T) = e^{\theta(T-N)} - 1 - \theta T e^{\theta(T-N)} + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2} e^{\theta(T-N)} + \theta N - \frac{N^2 \theta^2}{2}$, if $(T \geq N)$ then we have,

$$g'(T) = \theta e^{\theta(T-N)} - \theta^2 T e^{\theta(T-N)} - \theta e^{\theta(T-N)} - \theta^2 T e^{\theta(T-N)} + \frac{\theta^3 T^2}{2} e^{\theta(T-N)} = \frac{\theta^3 T^2}{2} e^{\theta(T-N)} > 0 \text{ if } (T \geq N).$$

So $g(T)$ is increasing on (N, ∞) and $g(T) > g(N) = \frac{\theta^2 N^2}{2} > 0$ if $(T > N)$. Consequently
 $e^{\theta(T-N)} - 1 - \theta T e^{\theta(T-N)} + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2} e^{\theta(T-N)} + \theta N - \frac{N^2 \theta^2}{2} > 0$, if $(T \geq N)$.

Lemma 2: $e^{\theta(T-M)} - 1 - \theta T e^{\theta(T-M)} + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2} e^{\theta(T-M)} + \theta M - \frac{N^2 \theta^2}{2} > 0$, if $(T \geq N)$.

Proof: Proof of the lemma will be similar of the above lemma.

Theorem 1: $TVC_1(T)$ is convex on $[W/D, \infty]$, $TVC_i(T)$ ($i = 2, 3, 4, 5$) and TVC are convex on $(0, \infty)$.

Proof: Firstly we shall proof the convexity of $TVC_1(T)$, $TVC_3(T)$, & $TVC_5(T)$.

From equations (2), (4) & (7) yield,

$$\begin{aligned} TVC'_1(T) &= TVC'_3(T) = TVC'_5(T) \\ &= -\frac{A}{T^2} + \frac{D\{\theta(c\theta + h) + H\}}{T^2\theta^3} (\theta T e^{\theta T} - e^{\theta T} + 1) - \frac{DH}{2\theta} \\ &\quad + \frac{cDI_k}{T^2\theta^2} [\theta T e^{\theta(T-N)} - e^{\theta(T-N)} + 1 - N\theta] + \frac{sDI_e N^2}{2T^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} TVC''_1(T) &= TVC''_3(T) = TVC''_5(T) \\ &= \frac{2A}{T^3} + \frac{2D\{\theta(c\theta + h) + H\}}{T^3\theta^3} \left\{ e^{\theta T} \left(1 - T\theta + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2} \right) - 1 \right\} \\ &\quad + \frac{2cDI_k}{T^3\theta^2} \left[e^{\theta(T-N)} - 1 - \theta T e^{\theta(T-N)} + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2} e^{\theta(T-N)} + N\theta \right] - \frac{sDI_e N^2}{T^3} \\ &\geq \frac{2A}{T^3} + \frac{2D\{\theta(c\theta + h) + H\}}{T^3\theta^3} \{ e^{\theta T} e^{-\theta T} - 1 \} \\ &\quad + \frac{2cDI_k}{T^3\theta^2} \left[e^{\theta(T-N)} - 1 - \theta T e^{\theta(T-N)} + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2} e^{\theta(T-N)} + N\theta - \frac{N^2 \theta^2}{2} \right] \\ &= \frac{2A}{T^3} + \frac{2cDI_k}{T^3\theta^2} \left[e^{\theta(T-N)} - 1 - \theta T e^{\theta(T-N)} + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2} e^{\theta(T-N)} + N\theta - \frac{N^2 \theta^2}{2} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 1 imply that $\frac{d^2TVC_1(T)}{dT^2} > 0$ and by similarity $\frac{d^2TVC_5(T)}{dT^2} > 0$ and $\frac{d^2TVC_3(T)}{dT^2} > 0$ if $(T \geq N)$. Hence, $TVC_1(T)$, $TVC_3(T)$, & $TVC_5(T)$ are convex on $\left[\frac{W}{D}, \infty\right)$, and $(0, \infty)$ respectively.

Secondly, we shall proof the convexity of $TVC_2(T)$ from equation (3) yield,

$$\begin{aligned} TVC_2'(T) = & -\frac{A}{T^2} + \frac{D\{\theta(c\theta + h) + H\}}{T^2\theta^3} (\theta Te^{\theta T} - e^{\theta T} + 1) - \frac{DH}{2\theta} \\ & + \frac{cDI_k}{T^2\theta^2} [\theta Te^{\theta(T-N)} - e^{\theta(T-N)} + 1 - N\theta] + \frac{sDI_e N^2}{2T^2} \\ & + \frac{cDI_p}{T^2\theta^2} [\theta Te^{\theta(T-M)} - e^{\theta(T-M)} + 1 - M\theta]. \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} TVC_2''(T) = & \frac{2A}{T^3} + \frac{2cDI_p}{T^3\theta^2} \left[e^{\theta(T-M)} - 1 - \theta Te^{\theta(T-M)} + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2} e^{\theta(T-M)} + M\theta \right] \\ & - \frac{sDI_e N^2}{T^3} + \frac{2cDI_k}{T^3\theta^2} \left[e^{\theta(T-N)} - 1 - \theta Te^{\theta(T-N)} + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2} e^{\theta(T-N)} + N\theta \right] \\ \geq & \frac{2A}{T^3} + \frac{2cDI_p}{T^3\theta^2} \left[e^{\theta(T-M)} - 1 - \theta Te^{\theta(T-M)} + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2} e^{\theta(T-M)} + M\theta - \frac{N^2\theta^2}{2} \right] \\ & + \frac{2cDI_k}{T^3\theta^2} \left[e^{\theta(T-N)} - 1 - \theta Te^{\theta(T-N)} + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2} e^{\theta(T-N)} + N\theta \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 1 & 2 implies that $\frac{d^2TVC_2(T)}{dT^2} > 0$.

Hence, $TVC_2(T)$ is convex on $(0, \infty)$.

Thirdly, we shall proof the convexity of $TVC_4(T)$ from equation (5) yield,

$$TVC_4''(T) = -\frac{A}{T^2} + \frac{D\{\theta(c\theta + h) + H\}}{T^2\theta^3} (\theta Te^{\theta T} - e^{\theta T} + 1) - \frac{DH}{2\theta} - \frac{sDI_e}{2} + I_e sD. \tag{10}$$

$$TVC_4''(T) = \frac{2A}{T^3} > 0.$$

Since $\frac{d^2TVC_4(T)}{dT^2} > 0$. Hence, $TVC_4(T)$ is convex on $(0, \infty)$.

Now, by combining the above argument we can say that $TVC(T)$ is convex on $T > 0$. These complete the proof.

4. DECISION RULES FOR THE OPTIMAL CYCLE TIME T^*

In this section, the present study demonstrates the determination of the optimal cycle time for the above two cases, under the condition of minimizing average total relevant costs.

Consider the following equations $TVC'_i(T) (i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5) = 0$, if roots of the equations exist for convenience, let $T_i^* (i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5)$ denote the root of equations by convexity

$$\begin{cases} < 0 & \text{if } T < T_i^* \\ = 0 & \text{if } T = T_i^* \\ > 0 & \text{if } T > T_i^* \end{cases}$$

imply that $TVC_i(T)$ is decreasing on $(0, T_i^*]$ and increasing on $[T_i^*, \infty)$ for all $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, \& 5$.

4.1 Case $(N < M \leq \frac{W}{D})$

Some lemmas are also helps us to get objective. Lemmas are following:

Proposition 1: let $P(T) = \theta T e^{\theta T} - e^{\theta T} + 1$ for $T > 0, \theta > 0$. Then $P(T) > 0$ for $T > 0, \theta > 0$.

Proof: Given $P(T) = \theta T e^{\theta T} - e^{\theta T} + 1$ for $T > 0, \theta > 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} P(T) &= \theta T (1 + \theta T + \dots) - (1 + \theta T + \dots) - 1 \\ &= \theta T (1 + \theta T + \dots) - \left(\theta T + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2!} + \dots \right) \\ &= \theta T + \theta T + \left(\theta T + \frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2!} + \frac{\theta^3 T^3}{3!} + \dots \right) - \left(\frac{\theta^2 T^2}{2!} + \frac{\theta^3 T^3}{3!} + \dots \right) - \theta T \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\theta^{n+1} T^{n+1}}{n!} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\theta^n T^n}{n!} > 0, \text{ if } T > 0, \theta > 0. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof.

Lemma 3: $TVC'_2(T) > TVC'_1(T)$ if $T > 0$.

Proof: From equations (8) & (9) $TVC'_2(T) - TVC'_1(T) > 0$. Hence the proof.

Now, from equations (8), (9) & (10), we get

$$TVC'_1(W/D) = \Delta_1$$

$$TVC_2'(W/D) = \Delta_2$$

$$TVC_2'(M) = TVC_3'(M) = \Delta_3$$

$$TVC_3'(N) = TVC_4'(N) = \Delta_4$$

$\Delta_1 > 0$ if and only if $TVC_1'(W/D) > 0$ if and only if $T_1^* < W/D$

$\Delta_2 > 0$ if and only if $TVC_2'(W/D) > 0$ if and only if $T_2^* < W/D$

$\Delta_3 > 0$ if and only if $TVC_2'(M) = TVC_3'(M) > 0$ if and only if $T_2^* < M, T_3^* < M$

$\Delta_4 > 0$ if and only if $TVC_3'(N) = TVC_4'(N) > 0$ if and only if $T_3^* < N, T_4^* < N$

By lemma 3, $\Delta_2 > \Delta_1 > \Delta_3 > \Delta_4$.

From above arguments, we can summarize the above results in Theorem 2.

Theorem 2: Suppose that $(N < M \leq)$ then

- (A) If $\Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_2 \geq 0, \Delta_3 \geq 0$ & $\Delta_4 \geq 0$ then $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_4^*)$, and $T^* = T_4^*$.
- (B) If $\Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_2 \geq 0, \Delta_3 \geq 0$ & $\Delta_4 < 0$ then $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_3^*)$, and $T^* = T_3^*$.
- (C) If $\Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_2 \geq 0, \Delta_3 < 0$ & $\Delta_4 < 0$ then $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_2^*)$, and $T^* = T_2^*$.
- (D) If $\Delta_1 < 0, \Delta_2 \geq 0, \Delta_3 < 0$ & $\Delta_4 < 0$ then $TVC(T^*) = \min \{TVC(T_1^*), TVC(T_2^*)\}$ and $T^* = T_1^*,$ or T_2^* .
- (E) If $\Delta_1 < 0, \Delta_2 < 0, \Delta_3 < 0$ & $\Delta_4 < 0$ then $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_1^*)$, and $T^* = T_1^*$.

Proof: (A) If $\Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_2 \geq 0, \Delta_3 \geq 0$ & $\Delta_4 \geq 0$ which implies that, $TVC_1'(W/D) \geq 0, TVC_2'(W/D) \geq 0, TVC_2'(M) = TVC_3'(M) \geq 0, TVC_3'(N) = TVC_4'(N) \geq 0$. Therefore, $T_1^* < W/D, T_2^* < W/D, T_2^* < M, T_3^* < M, T_3^* < N, T_4^* < N$ and

- (i) $TVC_1(T)$ is increasing on $[W/D, \infty)$.
- (ii) $TVC_2(T)$ is increasing on $[M, W/D]$.
- (iii) $TVC_3(T)$ is increasing on $[N, M)$.
- (iv) $TVC_4(T)$ is decreasing on $(0, T_4^*]$ and increasing on $[T_4^*, N)$.

Combining (i)-(iv), we conclude that $TVC(T)$ has the minimum value at $T = T_4^*$ on $(0, N)$ and at N . Hence $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_4^*)$ and T^* is T_4^* .

- (B) If $\Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_2 \geq 0, \Delta_3 \geq 0$ & $\Delta_4 < 0$ which implies that, $TVC_1'(W/D) \geq 0, TVC_2'(W/D) \geq 0, TVC_2'(M) = TVC_3'(M) \geq 0, TVC_3'(N) = TVC_4'(N) < 0$. Therefore, $T_1^* < W/D, T_2^* < W/D, T_2^* < M, T_3^* < M, T_3^* \geq N, T_4^* \geq N$ and
 - (i) $TVC_1(T)$ is increasing on $[W/D, \infty)$.
 - (ii) $TVC_2(T)$ is increasing on $[M, W/D]$.

(iii) $TVC_3(T)$ is decreasing on $[N, T_3^*]$ and increasing on $[T_3^*, M)$.

(iv) $TVC_4(T)$ is decreasing on $(0, N)$.

Combining (i)-(iv), we conclude that $TVC(T)$ has the minimum value at $T = T_3^*$ on $[N, M)$. Hence, $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_3^*)$ and T^* is T_3^* .

(C) If $\Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_2 \geq 0, \Delta_3 < 0$ & $\Delta_4 < 0$ which implies that, $TVC_1'(W/D) \geq 0, TVC_2'(W/D) \geq 0, TVC_2'(M) = TVC_3'(M) < 0, TVC_3'(N) = TVC_4'(N) < 0$. Therefore, $T_1^* < W/D, T_2^* < W/D, T_2^* \geq M, T_3^* \geq M, T_3^* \geq N, T_4^* \geq N$ and

(i) $TVC_1(T)$ is increasing on $[W/D, \infty)$.

(ii) $TVC_2(T)$ is increasing on $[M, W/D]$.

(iii) $TVC_3(T)$ is decreasing on $[N, T_3^*]$ and increasing on $[T_3^*, M)$.

(iv) $TVC_4(T)$ is decreasing on $(0, N)$.

Combining (i)-(iv), we conclude that $TVC(T)$ has the minimum value at $T = T_3^*$ on $[N, M)$. Hence $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_3^*)$ and T^* is T_3^* .

(D) If $\Delta_1 < 0, \Delta_2 \geq 0, \Delta_3 < 0$ & $\Delta_4 < 0$ which implies that, $TVC_1'(W/D) < 0, TVC_2'(W/D) \geq 0, TVC_2'(M) = TVC_3'(M) < 0, TVC_3'(N) = TVC_4'(N) < 0$. Therefore, $T_1^* \geq W/D, T_2^* < W/D, T_2^* \geq M, T_3^* \geq M, T_3^* \geq N, T_4^* \geq N$ and

(i.) $TVC_1(T)$ is decreasing on $[W/D, \infty)$.

(ii) $TVC_2(T)$ is decreasing on $[M, T_2^*]$ and increasing on $[T_2^*, W/D]$.

(iii) $TVC_3(T)$ is decreasing on $[N, M)$.

(iv) $TVC_4(T)$ is decreasing on $(0, N)$.

Combining (i)-(iv), we conclude that $TVC(T)$ has the minimum value at $T = T_1^*$ on $[W/D, \infty)$ and $TVC(T)$ has the minimum value at $T = T_2^*$ on $[M, W/D]$. Hence, $TVC(T^*) = \min \{TVC(T_1^*), TVC(T_2^*)\}$.

(E) If $\Delta_1 < 0, \Delta_2 < 0, \Delta_3 < 0$ & $\Delta_4 < 0$ which implies that, $TVC_1'(W/D) < 0, TVC_2'(W/D) < 0, TVC_2'(M) = TVC_3'(M) < 0, TVC_3'(N) = TVC_4'(N) < 0$. Therefore, $T_1^* \geq W/D, T_2^* \geq W/D, T_2^* \geq M, T_3^* \geq M, T_3^* \geq N, T_4^* \geq N$ and

(i) $TVC_1(T)$ is decreasing on $[W/D, T_1^*]$ and increasing on $[T_1^*, \infty)$.

(ii) $TVC_2(T)$ is decreasing on $[M, W/D]$.

(iii) $TVC_3(T)$ is decreasing on $[N, M)$.

(iv) $TVC_4(T)$ is decreasing on $(0, N)$.

Combining (i)-(iv), we conclude that $TVC(T)$ has the minimum value at $T = T_1^*$ on $[W/D, \infty)$. Hence, $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_1^*)$ and T^* is T_1^* .

4.2 Case ($N < W/D < M$)

$$\begin{aligned} TVC'_1(M) &= TVC'_5(M) = \Delta_3 \\ TVC'_5(W/D) &= TVC'_3(W/D) = \Delta_1 \\ TVC'_3(N) &= TVC'_4(N) = \Delta_4 \end{aligned}$$

From above equation, we also get,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_3 \geq 0 &\text{ if and only if } TVC'_1(M) = TVC'_5(M) \geq 0 \text{ if and only if } T_1^* < M, T_5^* < M \\ \Delta_1 \geq 0 &\text{ if and only if } TVC'_5(W/D) = TVC'_3(W/D) \geq 0 \text{ if and only if } T_5^* < W/D, T_3^* < W/D \\ \Delta_4 \geq 0 &\text{ if and only if } TVC'_3(N) = TVC'_4(N) \geq 0 \text{ if and only if } T_3^* < N, T_4^* < N \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3:

- (A) If $\Delta_3 \geq 0, \Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_4 \geq 0$ then $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_4^*)$ and $T^* = T_4^*$.
- (B) If $\Delta_3 \geq 0, \Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_4 < 0$ then $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_3^*)$ and $T^* = T_3^*$.
- (C) If $\Delta_3 \geq 0, \Delta_1 < 0, \Delta_4 < 0$ then $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_5^*)$ and $T^* = T_5^*$.
- (D) If $\Delta_3 < 0, \Delta_1 < 0, \Delta_4 < 0$ then $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_1^*)$ and $T^* = T_1^*$.

Proof: (A) If $\Delta_3 \geq 0, \Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_4 \geq 0$. So $TVC'_1(M) = TVC'_5(M) \geq 0, TVC'_5(W/D) = TVC'_3(W/D) \geq 0$ and $TVC'_3(N) = TVC'_4(N) \geq 0$. Therefore $T_1^* < M, T_5^* < M, T_5^* < W/D, T_3^* < W/D, T_3^* < N$ and $T_4^* < N$. Furthermore,

- (i) $TVC_1(T)$ is increasing on $[M, \infty)$.
- (ii) $TVC_5(T)$ is increasing on $[W/D, M)$.
- (iii) $TVC_3(T)$ is increasing on $[N, W/D)$.
- (iv) $TVC_4(T)$ is decreasing on $(0, T_4^*]$ and increasing on $[T_4^*, N)$.

Combining (i)-(iv), we conclude that $TVC(T)$ has the minimum value at $T = T_4^*$ on $(0, N)$. Hence $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_4^*)$ and $T^* = T_4^*$.

- (B) If $\Delta_3 \geq 0, \Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_4 < 0$. So $TVC'_1(M) = TVC'_5(M) \geq 0, TVC'_5(W/D) = TVC'_3(W/D) \geq 0$ and $TVC'_3(N) = TVC'_4(N) < 0$. Therefore, $T_1^* < M, T_5^* < M, T_5^* < W/D, T_3^* < W/D, T_3^* \geq N$ and $T_4^* \geq N$. Furthermore,

- (i) $TVC_1(T)$ is increasing on $[M, \infty)$.
- (ii) $TVC_5(T)$ is increasing on $[W/D, M)$.
- (iii) $TVC_3(T)$ is decreasing on $[N, T_3^*]$ and increasing on $[T_3^*, W/D)$.
- (iv) $TVC_4(T)$ is decreasing on $(0, N)$.

Combining (i)-(iv), we conclude that $TVC(T)$ has the minimum value at $T = T_3^*$ on $[N, W/D)$. Hence $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_3^*)$ and $T^* = T_3^*$.

(C) If $\Delta_3 \geq 0, \Delta_1 < 0, \Delta_4 < 0$. So $TVC'_1(M) = TVC'_5(M) \leq 0, TVC'_5(W \setminus D) = TVC'_3(W/D) < 0$ and $TVC'_3(N) = TVC'_4(N) < 0$. Therefore, $T_1^* < M, T_5^* < M, T_5^* \geq W/D, T_3^* \geq W/D, T_3^* \geq N$ and $T_4^* \geq N$. Furthermore,

- (i) $TVC_1(T)$ is increasing on $[M, \infty)$.
- (ii) $TVC_5(T)$ is decreasing on $[W/D, T_5^*]$ and increasing on $[T_5^*, M)$.
- (iii) $TVC_3(T)$ is decreasing on $[N, W/D)$.
- (iv) $TVC_4(T)$ is decreasing on $(0, N)$.

Combining (i)-(iv), we conclude that $TVC(T)$ has the minimum value at $T = T_5^*$ on $[W/D, M)$. Hence, $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_5^*)$ and $T^* = T_5^*$.

(D) If $\Delta_3 < 0, \Delta_1 < 0, \Delta_4 < 0$. So $TVC'_1(M) = TVC'_5(M) < 0, TVC'_5(W \setminus D) = TVC'_3(W/D) < 0$ and $TVC'_3(N) = TVC'_4(N) < 0$. Therefore, $T_1^* \geq M, T_5^* \geq M, T_5^* \geq W/D, T_3^* \geq W/D, T_3^* \geq N$ and $T_4^* \geq N$. Furthermore,

- (i) $TVC_1(T)$ is increasing on $[M, T_1^*]$ and increasing on $[T_1^*, \infty)$.
- (ii) $TVC_5(T)$ is decreasing on $[W/D, M)$.
- (iii) $TVC_3(T)$ is decreasing on $[N, W/D)$.
- (iv) $TVC_4(T)$ is decreasing on $(0, N)$.

Combining (i)-(iv), we conclude that $TVC(T)$ has the minimum value at $T = T_1^*$ on $[M, \infty)$. Hence, $TVC(T^*) = TVC(T_1^*)$ and $T^* = T_1^*$.

5. THE ALGORITHM

In this section, we shall combine the above results to outline the algorithm to help us to decide the optimal cycle time and optimal order quantity.

Step 1: if $(N < M \text{ d'' } W/D)$, then go to the step 2. Otherwise go to step3.

- Step 2:**
- (i) If $\Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_2 \geq 0, \Delta_3 \geq 0$ & $\Delta_4 \geq 0$ then T^* is T_4^* .
 - (ii) If $\Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_2 \geq 0, \Delta_3 \geq 0$ & $\Delta_4 < 0$ then T^* is T_3^* .
 - (iii) If $\Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_2 \geq 0, \Delta_3 < 0$ & $\Delta_4 < 0$ then T^* is T_2^* .
 - (iv) If $\Delta_1 < 0, \Delta_2 \geq 0, \Delta_3 < 0$ & $\Delta_4 < 0$ then T^* is T_1^* , or T_2^* associated with the least cost.
 - (v) If $\Delta_1 < 0, \Delta_2 < 0, \Delta_3 < 0$ & $\Delta_4 < 0$ then T^* is T_1^* .

- Step 3:**
- (i) If $\Delta_3 \geq 0, \Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_4 \geq 0$ then T^* is T_4^* .
 - (ii) If $\Delta_3 \geq 0, \Delta_1 \geq 0, \Delta_4 < 0$ then T^* is T_3^* .

(iii) If $\Delta_3 \geq 0, \Delta_1 < 0, \Delta_4 < 0$ then T^* is T_5^* .

(iv) If $\Delta_3 < 0, \Delta_1 < 0, \Delta_4 < 0$ then T^* is T_1^* .

According to the Intermediate Value Theorem (Thomas and Finney, 1996), the bisection method can be locate T_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$).

6. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

To illustrate the results. Let us apply the proposed method to solve the following numerical examples.

Example 1: If $D = 1000$ units/unit time, $W = 100$ units, $A = \$50$ /order, holding cost = $\$1$ / unit, $c = \$50$ /unit, $s = \$52$ /unit, $I_k = \$0.12$ /\$/year, $I_e = \$0.11$ /\$/year, $I_p = \$0.10$ /\$/year, $N = 0.10$ year, $M = 0.11$ year, and $\theta = 0.01$. Using step 2 (i) we get $T^* = T_4^* = 0.1176$ and $Q^* = 117.6$.

Example 2: If $D = 1000$ units/unit time, $W = 490$ units, $A = \$400$ /order, holding cost = $\$60$ / unit, $c = \$50$ /unit, $s = \$52$ /unit, $I_k = \$0.12$ /\$/year, $I_e = \$0.11$ /\$/year, $I_p = \$0.10$ /\$/year, $N = 0.10$ year, $M = 0.11$ year, and $\theta = 0.01$. Using step 2 (ii) we get $T^* = T_3^* = 0.2205$ and $Q^* = 220.5$.

Example 3: If $D = 1000$ units/unit time, $W = 480$ units, $A = \$400$ /order, holding cost = $\$10$ / unit, $c = \$50$ /unit, $s = \$52$ /unit, $I_k = \$0.12$ /\$/year, $I_e = \$0.11$ /\$/year, $I_p = \$0.10$ /\$/year, $N = 0.10$ year, $M = 0.11$ year, and $\theta = 0.01$. Using step 2 (iii) we get $T^* = T_2^* = 0.2003$ and $Q^* = 200.3$.

Example 4: If $D = 1000$ units/unit time, $W = 220$ units, $A = \$400$ /order, holding cost = $\$10$ / unit, $c = \$50$ /unit, $s = \$52$ /unit, $I_k = \$0.12$ /\$/year, $I_e = \$0.11$ /\$/year, $I_p = \$0.10$ /\$/year, $N = 0.10$ year, $M = 0.11$ year, and $\theta = 0.01$. Using step 2 (iv) we get $T^* = T_1^* = 0.2205$ and $Q^* = 220.5$.

Example 5: If $D = 1000$ units/unit time, $W = 500$ units, $A = \$20$ /order, holding cost = $\$30$ / unit, $c = \$100$ /unit, $s = \$120$ /unit, $I_k = \$0.15$ /\$/year, $I_e = \$0.11$ /\$/year, $I_p = \$0.10$ /\$/year, $N = 0.10$ year, $M = 0.11$ year, and $\theta = 0.01$. Using step 2 (v) we get $T^* = T_1^* = 0.0355$ and $Q^* = 35.50$.

Example 6: If $D = 1000$ units/unit time, $W = 100$ units, $A = \$50$ /order, holding cost = $\$60$ / unit, $c = \$50$ /unit, $s = \$52$ /unit, $I_k = \$0.15$ /\$/year, $I_e = \$0.11$ /\$/year, $I_p = \$0.10$ /\$/year, $N = 0.09$ year, $M = 0.11$ year, and $\theta = 0.01$. Using step 3 (i) we get $T^* = T_4^* = 0.0388$ and $Q^* = 38.80$.

Example 7: If $D = 1000$ units/unit time, $W = 109$ units, $A = \$270$ /order, holding cost = $\$60$ / unit, $c = \$50$ /unit, $s = \$52$ /unit, $I_k = \$0.15$ /\$/year, $I_e = \$0.11$ /\$/year, $I_p = \$0.10$ /\$/year, $N = 0.09$ year, $M = 0.11$ year, and $\theta = 0.01$. Using step 3 (ii) we get $T^* = T_3^* = 0.0902$ and $Q^* = 90.20$.

Example 8: If $D = 1000$ units/unit time, $W = 96$ units, $A = \$340/\text{order}$, holding cost = $\$60/\text{unit}$, $c = \$50/\text{unit}$, $s = \$52/\text{unit}$, $I_k = \$0.15/\text{\$/year}$, $I_e = \$0.11/\text{\$/year}$, $I_p = \$0.10/\text{\$/year}$, $N = 0.09\text{year}$, $M = 0.11$ year, and $\theta = 0.01$. Using step 3 (iii) we get $T^* = T_5^* = 0.1010$ and $Q^* = 101$.

Example 9: If $D = 1000$ units/unit time, $W = 100$ units, $A = \$450/\text{order}$, holding cost = $\$60/\text{unit}$, $c = \$50/\text{unit}$, $s = \$52/\text{unit}$, $I_k = \$0.15/\text{\$/year}$, $I_e = \$0.11/\text{\$/year}$, $I_p = \$0.10/\text{\$/year}$, $N = 0.09$ year, $M = 0.11$ year, and $\theta = 0.01$. Using step 3 (iv) we get $T^* = T_1^* = 0.1159$ and $Q^* = 115.9$.

7. CONCLUSION

The supplier offers the permissible delay in payments to the retailer in order to stimulate the demand. Hence, the assumption in previously published results that the fully permissible delay in payments is permitted under a sufficient quantity is practical. On the other hand, the permissible delay in payments will not be permitted when the order quantity is smaller than a predetermined quantity obviously is an extreme case. In this paper, the proposed model allows or relax the supplier to offer an alternative policy as DOQ (Displaying Order Quantity) policy, i.e., if retailer decreases order quantity just below to a sufficient quantity W which is decided by supplier, then take all benefits of trade credits offered by supplier, on giving small fine by retailer. This policy helps retailer to take decisions about ordering quantity free from predetermined quantity W . Therefore retailer can take all credit benefits with less ordering quantity by giving only small fine (I_p).

REFERENCES

- [1] F. J. Arcelus, N. H. Shah, and G. Srinivasan, (2001), Retailer's Response to Special Sales: Price Discount vs. Trade Credit, *OMEGA*, **29**: 417–428.
- [2] S. P. Aggarwal, and C. K. Jaggi, (1995), Ordering Policies of Deteriorating Items Under Permissible Delay in Payments, *J. Oper. Res. Soc.*, **46**: 658–662.
- [3] H.-J. Chang, and C.-Y. Dye, (2001), An Inventory Model for Deteriorating Items with Partial Backlogging and Permissible Delay in Payments, *Int. J. Syst. Sci.*, **32**: 345–352.
- [4] H.-J. Chang, C. H. Hung, and C.-Y. Dye, (2001), An Inventory Model for Deteriorating Items with Linear Trend Demand Under the Condition of Permissible Delay in Payments, *Prod. Plan. Control*, **12**: 274–282.
- [5] P. Chu, K.-J. Chung, and S.-P. Lan, (1998), Economic Order Quantity of Deteriorating Items Under Permissible Delay in Payments, *Comput. Oper. Res.*, **25**: 817–824.
- [6] K.-J. Chung, (1998), A Theorem on the Determination of Economic Order Quantity Under Conditions of Permissible Delay in Payments, *Comput. Oper. Res.*, **25**: 49–52.

- [7] P. M. Ghare, and G. P. Schrader, (1963), A Model for an Exponentially Decaying Inventory, *J. Indust. Eng.*, **14**: 238–243.
- [8] S. K. Goyal, (1985), Economic Order Quantity Under Conditions of Permissible Delay in Payments, *J. Oper. Res. Soc.*, **36**: 335–338.
- [9] A. M. Jamal, B. R. Sarker, and S. Wang, (1997), An Ordering Policy for Deteriorating Items with Allowable Shortage and Permissible Delay in Payment, *J. Oper. Res. Soc.*, **48**: 826–833.
- [10] H.-C. Liao, C.-H. Tsai, and C.-T. Su, (2000), An Inventory Model with Deteriorating Items Under Inflation when a Delay in Payment is Permissible, *Int. J. Prod. Econ.*, **63**: 207–214.
- [11] N. H. Shah, (1993), Probabilistic Time Scheduling Model for an Exponentially Decaying Inventory when Delay in Payments are Permissible, *Int. J. Prod. Eco.*, **32**: 77–82.
- [12] N. H. Shah, (1997), Probabilistic Order Level System with Lead-Time when Delay in Payments is Permissible, *TOP (Spain)*, **5**: 297–305.
- [13] J.-T. Teng, (2002), On Economic Order Quantity Under Conditions of Permissible Delay in Payments, *J. Oper. Res. Soc.*, **53**: 915–918.
- [14] J.-T. Teng, M.-S. Chern, H.-L. Yang, and Y. J. Wang, (1999), Deterministic Lot-Size Inventory Models with Shortages and Deterioration for Fluctuating Demand, *Oper. Res. Lett.*, **24**: 65–72.
- [15] H.-L. Yang, J.-T. Teng, and M.-S. Chern, (2001), Deterministic Inventory Lot-Size Models Under Inflation with Shortages and Deterioration for Fluctuating Demand, *Nav. Res. Logist.*, **48**: 144–158.

S. R. Singh

Department of Mathematics,
D. N. College Meerut (U.P.)
E-mail: shivrajpundir@yahoo.com

Pushpendra Saini

Department of Mathematics,
D. N. College Meerut (U.P.),
E-mail: pushpendrasaini22@gmail.com

Rekha Chaudhary

Department of Mathematics,
Government Engg. College, Bharatpur (Raj.),
E-mail: rekhaparth2003@yahoo.co.in